

**COMPENSATORY STRATEGIES AS A WAY TO FOSTER SPEAKING
OF STUDENTS WITH ELEMENTARY LEVEL**

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Annotation

The given article is intended to analyze the contribution of compensatory strategies in early periods of learning English as a second or foreign language. Furthermore, the informative research is provided with the ways to apply compensatory strategies in language teaching process.

Keywords: compensatory strategies, synonyms, linguistic clues, speaking improvement, exercises, adaptation and approximation, parallels

Introduction.

Compensatory strategies are such strategies “that allow students to use a foreign language for its understanding and reproduction, despite the lack of knowledge¹. Compensatory strategies are designed to make up for the lack of grammatical knowledge and especially vocabulary”². As for compensatory competence, its formation involves the development of the ability and willingness to overcome the deficit of one’s foreign language knowledge and skills, namely: to be able to if you don’t know a word, replace it with a synonym or a description of the concept, be able to restructure your statement ..., be able to “not get hung up” on the unfamiliar, etc. Thus, the value of compensatory competence is really great, because in the process of generating an utterance, students of a foreign language certainly encounter situations of a “stopper”, a lack of lexical units for expressing

¹ Compensation strategies. <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/professional-development/teachers/knowning-subject/c/compensation-strategies>

² Compensatory strategy.

<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/compensatory?ysclid=ljh36quqeu529352962>

thoughts, and the development of compensatory competence allows in most cases to avoid such difficulties and remove the language barrier. In the scientific literature and textbooks, this issue does not have sufficient coverage. At present, the problem of compensatory strategies, techniques, techniques in teaching foreign languages is becoming more and more relevant.

Main part.

Compensatory strategies include two main areas:

- Using intellectual guesswork.

Overcoming limitations, filling gaps in the process of speaking and writing. Let's consider the main strategies that can be successfully used to form and develop students' compensatory competencies in the process of teaching a foreign language.

- Use of guesswork.

When using a guess, it is supposed to rely on two types of clues: linguistic (linguistic) clues and extralinguistic (other). The use of linguistic clues is explained by the fact that compensatory competence is closely related to linguistic competence, since it includes knowledge of the structural elements of the language (grammatical, derivational, morphological, syntactic, lexical, phonetic) necessary for communication in the target language. The development of a language guess can be triggered by a number of exercises:

“Read the text and guess the meaning of the underlined words.”

"Read the words, offer their translation, based on the morphological analysis of the word."

"Read the underlined words and suggest their translation based on similar words in Russian (or the second language studied)."

- Use of anticipation (prediction)

In this case, the tasks are aimed at the formation of an extralinguistic guess. Students develop the skills to apply all the knowledge available to them in order to find the answer. To develop forecasting skills, you can use the following types of

tasks:

“Predicting the content of the text from photos or pictures.”

"Describe the image with attention to detail."

"Looking at the picture, determine who is the main character of the story."

“Read the title and identify the main idea of the text.”

“Read the words in the list before the text. What can be discussed in the text?”

“Read the passage of history. Suggest your ending.

- Adaptation or approximation

The strategy aims to simplify the oral and written responses of students. Adaptation skills are extremely important for the ability of students to independently design their statements, to follow their level. Tasks can be as follows:

“Mark the sentences in the text that express the main idea.”

“Complete the information from the text with your own examples.”

"Write abstracts to the text."

"Plan your text."

"Remove irrelevant information from the text."

Each of these strategies contributes to the development of compensatory competence in general.

Students avoid communication or experience fear, but do not abandon strategies (or responses) that are not very effective in learning or maintaining communication. Of course, such a strategy may owe its origin to some cultural reasons and serve to help "save face" for both the student and the teacher ³. However, regardless of cultural or any other motivation, refusal or avoidance of communication often contributes to the creation of an uncomfortable atmosphere, which can become an obstacle to further speech practice, and during the exam, negatively affect the student's grade. Teaching students positive communication strategies with limited vocabulary and grammar skills will improve both exam

³ Windle S. From Confusing to Confucian: Towards an Understanding. The Korea TESOL Journal, The English Connection, Nov. 2000, Vol. 4, № 6. P. 1–8.

scores and speaking practice and help students become more confident and competent in communication.

It should also be noted that maintaining or increasing student motivation is one of the problems that teachers face when working to improve language learning [Gardner, 1996, p.91]⁴. There is even a point of view that students with a high level of motivation get tired of classes in which too much attention is paid to form, instead of allowing them to interact in the language being studied⁵. In addition, students with a low level of motivation can become “more motivated” through successful interactions in the target language. Therefore, teaching students compensatory strategies can increase the degree of motivation and improve the potential of students for successful study, give them confidence. Compensatory strategies are important both for learning and for effective communication in the foreign language being studied⁶. Therefore, the formation of compensatory competence should begin already in elementary school. Younger students need to be helped to master the following skills and abilities:

1. Learn to draw parallels between the linguistic phenomena of the native and foreign languages: sounds, letters, letter combinations, words, phrases, sentences. For example, give as an example similar words in English and Russian (airport - аэропорт, vegan - вегетарианец; chocolate - шоколад, uzbek-узбек, media-медиа)
2. To learn how to compare the graphic image of a word with its sound image in the process of reading and writing (during the choral processing of the material, be sure to follow the text with your eyes; when prescribing words and sentences, whisper to yourself at the initial stage);

⁴ Gardner R. C. Social psychology and second language learning: the role of attitudes and motivation. London: Edward Arnold, 1985. 91–93 p.

⁵ Abdesslem H. Communication Strategies or Discourse Strategies in Foreign Language Performance. International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching. Sheffield UK, 1996, 34(1). P. 49–62

⁶ Kim D. D. I. & Margolis D. P. Korean student exposure to English listening and speaking: instruction, multimedia, travel. The Korea TESOL Journal, 2000, Vol. 3, № 1. P. 25–29.

3. Learn to use a language guess in the process of reading and listening, containing unfamiliar words and expressions (when explaining unfamiliar words, the teacher can use facial expressions and gestures to achieve maximum understanding, and later use the same movements to recall these words);
4. Learn to predict the content of the text by the title of the text, use various supports for this, such as pictures, subheadings, tables (for this, it is useful to analyze all the accompanying prompts with students before reading / listening);
5. Learn to ignore lexical difficulties, not to focus on the unfamiliar (in this case, we mean information that does not affect the understanding of the text, otherwise the exercise is preceded by a pre-text task with an explanation of key concepts);
6. Learn how to compose monologues, dialogues and written texts according to the proposed model or plan;
7. Learn to group lexical units according to the grammatical and thematic feature and subsequently use these materials (compose the so-called "mind maps" - a method of structuring concepts using graphic notation in the form of a diagram);
8. Develop the skill of guessing when reading the text (as an example, we can give an exercise with missing words data (optional) in a separate box)
9. Apply the learned grammatical rules in the process of verbal communication (encourage students to use new grammatical structures, pushing them with the proposed communicative situation);
10. Use reference material (dictionaries, tables, charts, rules).

All of the above skills and abilities will help the primary school student subsequently compensate for the language deficit. But, of course, the main condition for the successful implementation of compensatory techniques is the active assimilation of the corresponding language minimum.

Conclusion.

Thus, compensatory competence contributes to the speech activity of students, removes the language barrier, gives students confidence in their abilities, motivates them to learn foreign languages, teaches them to overcome difficulties, and at the same time has a general developmental impact on the student's personality.

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